

AN IMPROVED META-HEURISTIC ORIENTED EARLY SIZE ESTIMATION UTILIZING ABC

Manisha¹

Research Scholar, U.I.E.T (M.D.U), Rohtak, India
mvmanishavatsa@gmail.com

Dr. Rahul Rishi²

Professor, U.I.E.T (M.D.U), Rohtak, India
rahulrishi@mdurohtak.in

Abstract: *In order to channelize a team's effort in a fruitful direction any software oriented environment, pre-analysis of software components and the budget has always been useful practice. Estimation of the size becomes a tedious task when the machine is not trained well enough to provide good classification accuracy. In order to attain significant result when it comes to early prediction, the selection of the attribute set plays a vital role. Feature set selection has gained popularity in the last couple of years to make the classification process more precise. This paper utilizes and enhances the current behaviour architecture of Artificial Bee Colony (ABC), a meta-heuristic inspired algorithm is being used for feature vector selection. The data is further trained and classified by multiple multi-class classifiers. The evaluation of the results has been made on the base of quantitative parameter analysis and the co-relation of effort and size has also been presented. The paper utilizes dataset supported by NASA research frames.*

Keywords: *Software Size Estimation, Meta-Heuristics, Artificial Bee Colony (ABC).*

I. INTRODUCTION

The significance of software design can be summarised as a significant mixture of size and quality. A design creates software representations that can be evaluated for consistency [1]. The only way to correctly convert a customer's specifications into a finished software product is by design. Software design is the mechanism by which an agent establishes a specification for a software artefact that is intended to achieve goals and uses a collection of primitive components while adhering to constraints. A software design involves the estimation of total number of manpower needed to complete the work, total amount of other supplies and if the software project is extended or does not get complete on time, what would be the extra cost that would be applied to the design company. In order to save effort and to reduce computation complexity, pre-analysis of the software projects is required. NASA, the well-known organization of the world has submitted an analysed data based on the software projects which has been undertaken by NASA. In order to reduce the human effort, the system must be trained to deal with real time existing issues and architecture.

The software program is costly to develop and has a high cost due to its large size in the commercial informational systems. The degree of investment in software programs is estimated to be more than \$200 billion yearly. Boehm suggested carefully considering costs and the benefits before giving the needed resources for the software project. Generally, the precision of the software investment decisions has a direct impact on the quality of the software. Many times the costs for the project are underestimated, due to which many projects running are abandoned midway. This dropping of the project can be due to large costs consumption which was not estimated at an early stage or due to the wrong estimation of time and the resources needed. On the other hand, when the costs are overestimated, exaggerated project estimations may increase the project cost by putting less pressure on programmers to be creative. Moreover, in these cases sometimes the potential projects are rejected because of high cost or time. Resulting in the lost opportunity of creating a value-added project in the firm [2].

So, equally overestimation and under-estimation may cause costly errors. Hence, the accurate estimation of the project is purely needed for the reduction of excessive cost and lead to an increase in efficiency of the company [3]. The cost of the software projects are increasing day by day due to which the result of estimation errors can lead to bad consequences, so these estimations are equally significant or play an important role in project understanding and selection.

Estimating the development of the software has always remained a complicated problem. Improvement in these software estimation techniques leads to the more effective management of cost, time in the management of software. Software development contains numerous interrelated factors that affect the effort and productivity of the development process.

The important factors of size estimation which are generally considered in all the project estimation models are as follows:

- a) Time to be consumed in creating the project.
- b) Total human resources required for completing the project.
- c) Output quantity.

Software size estimation is a very critical issue to both designers and users. They can be used for producing requests for offers, contract talks, planning, and managing. Underestimating the sizes may consequence in management easily approving the project and then if the budget exceeds the failure of the project may occur as it may have underdeveloped functions and poor quality [4]. Overestimating may outcome in various resources dedicated to the project which can lead to loss of jobs.

Precise estimation of size is vital because:

1. It helps for classifying and ranking/arranging the development projects in terms of the overall business plan.
2. It is used for determining the resources needed for the project and at which interval which particular resource will be committed to which task.
3. The impact of changes can be easily viewed and assessed and re-planning can be easily done.
4. When resources are easily matched to the tasks then the project can be easily managed

Software size estimation includes the calculation of the following estimates:

1. Effort (usually in person-months)
2. Project duration (in calendar time)
3. Cost (in dollars)

For size estimation of any software, there are a large number of techniques are available. Machine learning (ML) is one of the most important techniques used to measure software cost estimation. There are a large number of shortcomings in previous methods that are applied for software effort estimation. So, ML is used to improve the shortcomings of the existing techniques. The choice of the learning category is depend upon the task.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

As the size of the software is dependent upon a lot of factors, this research articles sticks to the correlation of effort to software size and hence the literature survey is oriented towards machine learning and software effort to size estimation only.

Nanda et al. 2016 represented a model that is integrated neuro-fuzzy optimized with Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) to improve effort estimation on software projects of NASA dataset.

The Neuro-fuzzy algorithm is used for result optimization as well as training. The performance of the proposed model is computed with the comparison of another intelligent system model. The parameters that are computed such as Magnitude of Relative Error (MMER), Mean Standard Error (MSE), and Level Prediction. The proposed model represents better results as compared to others [5].

Novitasari et al. 2016 examine the use of PSO in conjunction with simulated annealing to improve SVM parameter selection. Proposed a local best PSO with SVR for software effort estimation with two objective functions including fitness and cost functions to measure the most favorable generated solution. The major criteria used for determining an acceptable solution is to have an optimization that enhances the fitness value or minimizes the cost value. The optimization is obtained by a cost-typed function, to minimize the error. Desharnais dataset is taken into consideration where local best PSO-SVR gives optimal cost [6].

Langsari et al. 2017 introduced the use of Gaussian Membership Function (GMF) FL and Multi-Objective PSO algorithms in calibrating and optimizing the COCOMO II model parameters. The proposed method is applied to the Nasa93 dataset. MOPSO is a calibration and optimization algorithm approach to improving the accurate degree of the COCOMO II model by optimizing its parameters. The proposed method gives significance in reduced MMRE and evaluation results have shown that the calibration and optimization with the proposed method gives an improved estimation compared to the basic COCOMO II model [7]. Following this, **Yigit-Sert and Kullu 2018** had also implemented ABC for software estimation work on similar dataset statistics [8].

Ali et al. 2019 presented a systematic review based upon recent studies related to software effort estimation models by applying machine learning approaches. The literature of the proposed work is based upon the previous studies that were published from January 1991 to December 2017. From the past studies, 75 were selected, then perform filtering of inclusion/exclusion and quality assessment. Most of the studies applied ANN as a machine learning model to compute the better mean magnitude of relative error (MMRE). Support Vector Machine (SVM) and ANN are mostly used as machine learning models rather than others [9].

Sehra et al. 2019 proposed a hybrid model which combines machine learning algorithms to predict the effort more accurately. The fuzzy analytic hierarchy process (FAHP) has been used effectively for feature ranking. Ranks generated from FAHP have been integrated into weighted kernel least square SVM for effort estimation. The combination

of weights generated by FAHP and SVM has resulted in more accurate effort estimates [10].

Chhabra et al. 2020 designed a FIS to optimize fuzzy logic-based COCOMO using PSO Algorithm to calculate the effect of cost parameters used in Intermediate COCOMO. PSO is used to solve the problem of parametric optimization of fuzzy systems. The magnitude of the relative error and its mean, calculated using COCOMO NASA2 and COCOMO NASA datasets are used as evaluation metrics to validate the proposed model. The model outperforms when compared to other optimization techniques. This fuzzy model handled the vagueness and ambiguity in information resulting in improved prediction accuracy of COCOMO. The resultant MMRE showed even more improved results in comparison to fuzzy-model-based COCOMO [11].

Suresh & Behera 2020 presented a comparative analysis based upon different models like; SVM, NN, RF, KNN, and back propagation algorithm. The orange data mining tool is used in the proposed work. Two datasets are used in the proposed work that is COCOMO'81 having 63 projects and the Desharnais dataset consists of 81 projects. The simulation results show that the back propagation model provides efficient results as compared to other approaches [12].

Rankovic et al. 2021 proposed two different architectures based upon Artificial Neural Network (ANN) that is used for software effort estimation. The author applied ANN as a machine learning approach due to its high speed of learning that helps to obtain better results. The main aim of the proposed work is to minimization of the Magnitude Relative Error (MRE) in effort estimation with the help of Taguchi's Orthogonal Arrays. It helps to find out the simple architecture of ANN for optimized learning. The proposed work is used to cover up different values of actual efficiency that belong to a huge range of projects. It helps to reduce the risk of error estimation to increase the rate of completed software projects [13].

Rhmann et al. 2021 introduced software effort estimation depends on the weighted hybrid search-based algorithm. The weighted ensembles were created by using various metaheuristic algorithms such as; black hole optimization, firefly algorithm, and genetic algorithm. The author used three datasets that are collected from the PROMISE repository. The simulation results were performed in R programming language using RKEEL and Metaheuristics Opt r packages. The results describe that the proposed metaheuristics based on weighted ensembles of hybrid search-based algorithms provide better results of software effort estimation [14].

As a result, it is recommended that a Neuro-based methodology be used to develop a suitable

generic form of model that can be used to estimate software effort for all types of projects. The authors proposed that NN-based techniques be used to create a generic form of model that can be used to estimate software effort for all types of projects.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed methodology is divided into three steps architecture. The first step loads the dataset and applies machine learning based improved k-means algorithm to divide the data into three sizes depending upon the co-relation attained in the groups. The second part applied Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) to select attribute sets from each divided group and the third step used training and classification algorithms to classify the test data. The proposed methodology ends up with summarizing the co-relation between the size and the effort. The overall methodology can be represented by the following algorithmic pseudo code.

A. Algorithm: CC = Estimation (PR)

Where, PR \rightarrow Project Records (Input)

CC \rightarrow Classified Class (Output)

1. Collect all the data records from the repository and create a Dataset
2. Aggregated_Dataset = Aggregate (Dataset) // Aggregate the collected dataset
3. Apply Iterative K-means
4. **For each data in range(Dataset)**
5. New_Data = Iterative K-means (Aggregated_Dataset) // According to the improved k-means [15] which consist of different similarity measures
6. **End – For**
7. Apply K-means on New_Data
8. Set an estimated cluster (C)
9. Calculate size of New_Data in terms of [Row, Col.]
10. Define initial C-Data = [] // To store clustered data
11. Consider Centroid C = C1, C2, & C3
12. **For X in to range(Row)**
13. **For Y in range(Col)**
14. **If Data (X, Y) \in C1**
15. C-Data 1 = New_Data (X, Y)
16. **Else if Data (X, Y) \in C2**
17. C-Data 2 = New_Data (X, Y)
18. **Else Data (i,j) \in C3**
19. C-Data 3 = New_Data (X, Y)
20. **End – If**
21. **Using the average**, adjust the value of Centroid C
22.
$$C = \frac{\text{sum}(C\text{-Data } 1, C\text{-Data } 2, \text{ and } C\text{-Data } 3 \text{ n})}{3}$$
23. **End – For**

24. $[K_{index}, K_{centroids}] = (C, 3)$ // K_{index} contains the centroid index, it would be either 1, 2 or 3 as the entire dataset is to be divided into three subsequent groups namely {high, moderate and low}

25. **End – For**

26. $K_{class} = identify\ unique\ identifies\ in\ K_{index}$
// Find all the unique classes

27. **For Z in range(K_{class})** // for each class category in the dataset

28. $Dataset_{sub} =$
 $Find(Dataset.identifiers == K_{class})$ // Find object of K_{class} in dataset identifiers

29. **End – For**

30. Apply ABC for co-relation analysis among the class object

31. $Employed_{Bees} = Dataset_sub.Record(count)$ // Find total number of elements in the specific class

32. $Employed_{food} = Dataset.Employed_{Bees}$ // Find attribute set of employed bees

33. Initiate Onlooker $_{Bee} = []$ // Initialize an empty array of onlooker bees

34. **For each emp in Employed $_{Bees}$** // take each bee food individually

35. $N_{bee_food} = Apply_Fuzzy_Normalization$ ($Employed_{Food}$) // Normalize the food behaviour by applying fuzzy logic

36. $Onlooker_{Bee} =$
 $(\sum_{i=2}^{N_{bee_food} \cdot length.Currenthive} \sum_{j=1}^{atlen} N_{bee_food_{i,j}} \times FlyChange) / (\sum_{i=2}^{Otherhives} \sum_{j=1}^{atlen} N_{bee_food_{i,j}} \times FlyChange)$ // The onlooker bee evaluates the employed bee based on the behaviours attained in the current cluster and average change occurred in the behaviour of the other hive nest bees according to the fitness

37. Define bee fitness
 $Fitness\ Function =$
 1 if $Employed_{bee_food} < Onlooker_bee_{food}$ //
 0 Otherwise
Bee fitness function

38. **If Fitness Function == 1**

39. Select the record from New_Data

40. **Else**

41. Reject the record from New_Data

42. **End – If**

43. Select record if the fitness value is 1, else reject the value

44. **End – For**

45. If the Bee food is accepted, the attribute set will be selected to subsequent category and pass categorized set to training

46. Initialize training algorithm and train the model

47. Structure = Train (Selected Data)

48. CC = Structure (Test Data)

49. **Return:** CC as Classified Class

50. End – Algorithm

The proposed algorithm architecture returns the categorized class value and then the difference of the actual categorized class and the simulation value is compared to each other. A fuzzy rule set is applied to predict the size in such case as mentioned in table I.

TABLE I: FUZZY SET

If $classified_{label} > 30\%$ margin	Very high software size not beneficial as a project
Else if $Classified_{label} > 10\%$ margin and $Classified_{label} < 30\%$ margin	Moderate in software size and manageable if handled carefully
If Classified Label < 10% Margin	Low in computation and highly profitable as a project

According to the fuzzy set, if the classified label by the neural classifier, has a difference of more than 30% either in upward direction or in the downward direction, the estimated size would be high and that would result into higher computation complexity. Such projects will not be beneficial for the company and should be avoided in future. On the other hand, if the difference lies between 10-30%, the project is said to be moderately complex in terms of size and computation, and can be considered to hire. The third case is the most profitable case and has least computation complexity and size as compared to other existing projects. The evaluation of the quantitative parameters is illustrated in the result section.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The evaluation of the results has been made on the base of following parameters:

- a) Classification Accuracy
- b) Classification Cost Ratio

The classification cost ratio is the ratio of the classification accuracy attained by the proposed method to the classification accuracy attained by other algorithm in percentage. To justify the effectiveness of the proposed work the achieved classification accuracy is compared against two existing work based on ABC and CS. The classification accuracy of the three works is listed in table II.

TABLE II. CLASSIFICATION ACCURACY

Total Number of Projects	Accuracy enhanced ABC	Accuracy normal ABC [Venkata et al. (2020)] [16]	Accuracy normal cuckoo[Kaushik et al. (2017)] [15]
25	0.642	0.543	0.521
30	0.660	0.545	0.523
35	0.689	0.554	0.523
40	0.706	0.561	0.525
45	0.709	0.569	0.530
50	0.714	0.593	0.532
55	0.725	0.613	0.534
60	0.735	0.627	0.537
65	0.791	0.634	0.538
70	0.825	0.662	0.540
75	0.902	0.694	0.547
80	0.921	0.725	0.552
85	0.932	0.741	0.559
90	0.956	0.771	0.568
92	0.967	0.8008	0.571

As the utilized dataset was limited to 92 projects only the proposed algorithm simulated some more records for reference. A total of 5000 simulations were performed on the later stage and it is identified as the overall accuracy attained after 5000 simulation is 15% more efficient as compared to existing average accuracy. The average classification accuracy of 0.79 was exhibited by the proposed work, 0.64 by Venkata et al. and 0.54 by Kaushik et al. The CCR is further computed using by evaluating the proposed classification accuracy over the classification accuracy of the existing work. The CCR of the proposed work in comparison to the two existing works is depicted in Fig. 1.

The average CCR of the proposed work over the Venkata et al. who had implemented ABC based architecture is observed to be 1.236. However, CCR of proposed work for the Kaushik et al. work who had taken advantage of CS is observed to be 1.466. The figure depicts that on an average, if the proposed algorithm architecture is not used, the major loss could be upto 87% if the number of projects are small in count. It is obvious that, if the learning algorithm will get more data, it will produce much precise classification value. The outcome of the paper can be extended by hybridizing the model value with other meta-heuristics algorithms.

Fig. 1 CCR of the proposed work over existing work

V. CONCLUSION

The paper had introduced a meta-heuristic inspired algorithm for early size estimation. To achieve this feature selection was performed using ABC fitness function. The multiclass classifier was used for the training and classification of the data obtained from the NASA that has been used as the base for the analysis by numerous existing studies. The evaluation of the proposed enhanced ABC is performed in terms of classification accuracy achieved against variation in the number of projects. The work further outperformed in terms of CCR computed against the existing works demonstrating CCR of 1.236 and 1.466. This shows that the reliable and cost effective size estimations using proposed work.

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